

Study of Clinical Characteristics and Pathogenesis of Staphylococcus Aureus in Patients in Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Hassan Mushin Hassan¹ & Muslim Abbas Allu^{2*}

¹General and laparoscopic surgeon, FIBMS, College of medicine, University of Dohuk

²Nursing Department, Technical Institute of Zakho/ Duhok, University of Duhok polytechnic

* Corresponding Author: Muslim Abbas Allu, Email: muslim.allu@dpu.edu.krd

APA citation: Hassan, H.M., & Allu, M.A. (2025). Study of Clinical Characteristics and Pathogenesis of Staphylococcus Aureus in Patients in Kurdistan Region, Iraq. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 5(3), 122-125

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 23 Sep 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Staphylococcus aureus Epidemiology Pathogenesis Clinical Characteristics and Treatment Iraq</p>	<p>Staphylococcus aureus are Gram-positive, catalase positive cocci belonging to genus Staphylococcus in the family Staphylococcaceae, order Bacillales. They are approximately 0.5-1.5 µm in diameter, non-motile, non-spore-forming, facultative anaerobes that usually form in clusters. Staphylococcus aureus are ubiquitous and are a part of the normal skin flora of animals and humans. This organism does not normally cause infections on healthy skin however, if it is allowed to enter the bloodstream or internal tissues, these bacteria causes a variety of potentially serious infections. In humans, Staphylococcus aureus causes various supportive diseases, food poisoning, pneumonia and toxic shock syndrome. Staphylococcus aureus produces many virulence factors, such as hemolysis, leukocidins, enterotoxins, exfoliates toxin. caused by this pathogen are common both in community-acquired and hospital-acquired settings. The treatment remains challenging due to the emergence of multi-drug resistant strains such as MRSA (Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus). This review comprehensively covers the Epidemiology, Pathogenesis, clinical Characteristics and Treatment in Patients in Iraq.</p>

1. Introduction

Approximately 30% of the human population is colonized with *S. aureus* [5]. Staphylococcus aureus to cause infections is related to expression of these virulence factors. All these allow bacteria to adhere to tissues causing pathogenesis and invade the immune system causing toxic effect [6]. MRSA is a well-known pathogen of human and animals most commonly isolated from clinical cases. Problems arise during the treatment, in case MRSA strains occur. Despite all the measures taken in livestock breeding, the incidence of Staphylococcus aureus persists in the environment, in milk, on the animal's body, and also in humans [7]. Once exposed to MRSA, animals become reservoir of infection for human beings [8]. Increased antimicrobial resistance of the organisms in animals treated with antibiotics is the most common health issue worldwide and to over-come this problem, many natural antimicrobial compounds have been attracting many researchers' attention in the development of novel therapies for infections caused by the multi-drug-resistant Staphylococcus aureus [9, 10]. Members of the genus Staphylococcus are Gram-positive bacteria that are cocci-shaped; tend to be arranged in clusters and described as "grape-like." The genus Staphylococci- Although Staphylococcus is commensals of the skin, mucous membranes, alimentary and urogenital tracts of a diverse group of mammals and birds, they have been implicated in clinical infections of humans and animals [1]. Among the Coagulase-Positive Staphylococci isolated from clinical materials collected from humans, Staphylococcus aureus is the most important one [2]. In animals, the remaining species of Coagulase-Positive Staphylococci are far more common and clinically relevant [3]. Staphylococcus aureus in humans, Staphylococcus aureus is associated with many diseases, from less serious skin problems to very serious infections such as bacteremia and pneumonia. Infections are common both in community-acquired as well as hospital-acquired settings. It does not normally cause infection on healthy skin; however, if it is allowed to enter the blood-stream or internal tissues, these bacteria may cause a variety of potentially serious infections [4]. Staphylococcus aureus causes various supportive diseases, food poisoning, pneumonia and toxic shock syndrome. In addition, Staphylococcus aureus, especially MRSA, often causes serious problems via nosocomial infection in hospitals. Furthermore, community-acquired MRSA has recently emerged and has been re-reported to cause serious infectious diseases, sepsis, and

pneumonia -*S. aureus* is found in the environment and is also found in normal human flora, located on the skin and mucous membranes (most often the nasal area) of healthiest individuals [5]. The pathogenic success of *S. aureus* is primarily attributed to its extensive virulence factors, enabling it to adhere to host tissues, evade immune responses, and damage host cells [11]. Surface proteins such as clumping factors (ClfA, ClfB) and fibronectin-binding proteins facilitate adhesion to host cells and tissues. At the same time, secreted toxins like α-hemolysin, Panton-Valentine leukocidin (PVL), and toxic shock syndrome toxin-1 (TSST-1) contribute to tissue destruction and systemic toxicity [12]. Furthermore, its ability to form robust biofilms on medical devices and prosthetic implants enhances persistence by shielding bacteria from antimicrobial agents and host defenses, driving chronic and recurrent infections [13]. The clinical management of *S. aureus* infections is further complicated by its extraordinary capacity to acquire and develop antibiotic resistance. The emergence of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) in both healthcare and community settings has rendered many first-line antibiotics ineffective, leading to higher morbidity and mortality rates globally [14]. In recent decades, strains with reduced susceptibility to vancomycin (VRSA) and resistance to last-resort antibiotics highlighted the pathogen's evolutionary adaptability [15]. Understanding the genetic and molecular mechanisms driving antibiotic resistance and the evolutionary dynamics of resistant strains is essential for developing novel therapeutic approaches and public health strategies [16,17]. Given its clinical significance and the urgent challenges posed by antimicrobial resistance (AMR), *S. aureus* remains a critical global research focus. Therefore, the objective is to give general review on Staphylococcus aureus and to overview current situation in emergence of infections caused by drug-resistant Staphylococcus aureus. In addition, this review comprehensively covers the Epidemiology, Pathogenesis, clinical Characteristics and Treatment in Patients in Iraq.

2. Epidemiology

Staphylococcus aureus is harmless and reside normally on the skin and mucous membranes of humans and animals. This pathogen is distributed worldwide. Rates of infection in community settings and residents of nursing home increased risk of acquiring MRSA [19]. Staphylococcus

aureus (including drug-resistant strains such as MRSA) are found on the skin and mucous membranes, and humans are the major reservoir for these organisms [22,24]. It is estimated that up to half of all adults are colonized, and approximately 15% of the population persistently carry *S. aureus* in the anterior nares. Some populations tend to have higher rates of *S. aureus* colonization (up to 80%), such as health care workers, persons who use needles on a regular basis (i.e., diabetics and intravenous (IV) drug users), hospitalized patients, and immunocompromised individuals. *S. aureus* can be transmitted person-to-person by direct contact or by fomites [23,25]. Nasal carriage of *S. aureus* is most common, and increases with health care exposure, diabetes, dialysis, substance drug use, and human immunodeficiency virus infection [19]. While most carriers of *S. aureus* do not go on to develop illness, colonization often precedes infections. aureus bacteremia remains a common cause of bloodstream infection. It has an annual population-based incidence rate upwards of 50 cases/100,000 population and mortality rate approximating 20%-30% in developed countries despite effective antibacterial therapies and source control strategies [20]. In contrast, 30-day mortality from an acute myocardial infarction approximates 10% [21]. Patients with *S. aureus* bacteremia have a spectrum of clinical presentations; some are asymptomatic with incidentally identified primary bacteremia, while others have a sustained bloodstream infection complicated by embolic phenomena. The mechanism of disease from *S. aureus* is not well understood and thought to be mediated by the relationship between host susceptibility and pathogen virulence factors.

3. Pathogenesis

S. aureus is a highly adaptable and opportunistic pathogen that can colonize various anatomical sites, evade the host immune system, and cause a broad spectrum of infections. Its pathogenic potential is driven by a complex interplay of virulence factors that facilitate adherence, invasion, immune evasion, and tissue destruction [27]. *S. aureus* are one of the most common bacterial infections in humans and are the causative agents of multiple human infections, including bacteremia, infective endocarditis, skin and soft tissue infections (e.g., impetigo, folliculitis, furuncles, carbuncles, cellulitis, scalded skin syndrome, and others), osteomyelitis, septic arthritis, prosthetic device infections, pulmonary infections (e.g., pneumonia and empyema), gastroenteritis, meningitis, toxic shock syndrome, and urinary tract infections [25]. Depending on the strains involved and the site of infection, these bacteria can cause invasive infections and/or toxin-mediated diseases [25,26]. *S. aureus* is an uncommon cause of bacterial meningitis, accounting for 4.9 to 6.4% of cases 28-33. *S. aureus* meningitis may either arise by hematogenous spread from a non-CNS focus of infection or be secondary to neurosurgical intervention [34,35]. Hematogenous *S. aureus* meningitis is usually community acquired [29-35] and, compared with postsurgical *S. aureus* meningitis, typically affects older individuals (mean age of 59 years versus 40 years; $P = 0.04$) [36]. with severe medical comorbidities such as diabetes or chronic kidney disease [29-36]. When *Staphylococcus aureus* enters the skin, neutrophils and macrophages migrate to the site of infection. *Staphylococcus aureus* evades this response in a multitude of ways, including blocking chemotaxis of leukocytes, sequestering host antibodies, hiding from detection and destruction after ingestion by phagocytes [37]. In addition to SSTIs, pyogenic bacterial abscesses can form in deeper tissues, such as underlying muscle, and bacteria can disseminate to form abscesses at distal sites and affect virtually any internal organ system. *Staphylococcus aureus* produces an array of potential virulence factors that play an important role on every level of host-pathogen interactions, including immune evasion molecules that allow bacteria to circumvent host innate and adaptive immunity. A multitude of these virulence factors protects *Staphylococcus aureus* from bactericidal activity of PMNs or directly alters neutrophil function [38]. *Staphylococcus aureus* has the ability to cause PMN lysis. motory molecules, uncontrolled lysis can have pivotal consequences to host health and additionally can promote dissemination of bacteria previously contained within phagosomes. Recent studies revealed that after PMN engulfment, *Staphylococcus aureus* is able to divert PMNs from conventional apoptotic pathways and cause subsequent lysis of these host cells by means of a process termed programmed necrosis [39]. Notably, bacterial burden plays an essential role in directing PMNs toward programmed necrosis in addition to triggering programmed necrosis, *Staphylococcus aureus* secretes virulence factors that promote direct lysis of neutrophils. Among them are leukotoxins, such as Pantone-Valentine leukocidin, *Staphylococcus aureus* virulence factors. This pore-forming

cytotoxin is freely secreted by *Staphylococcus aureus* as a water-soluble monomer, and then binds the surface of target cells, forming a heptameric transmembrane pore. Formation of functional pores leads to cell death [40]. *Staphylococcus aureus* produces a number of membrane-damaging toxins capable of forming pores in the cytoplasmic membrane of host cells leading to cell lysis. Bi-component leukocidins form an octameric structure of alternating bi-layer of the host cytoplasmic membrane resulting in lysis. α -toxin that binds to the complement receptors C5aR and C5L2 on the surface of neutrophils [41]. Enterotoxins released by *Staphylococcus aureus* is leading cause of food poisoning, resulting from the consumption of food contaminated with enterotoxins. *Staphylococcal* food intoxication involves rapid onset of nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, cramps, and diarrhea. Symptoms usually resolve after 24 hours [42]. Scalded skin syndrome is caused by exfoliative toxins secreted on the epidermis resulting in conditions such as blisters, skin loss, pimples, furuncles, impetigo, and secondary infection [43].

4. Clinical Characteristics

Staphylococcus aureus (staph) infections cause a wide range of symptoms, from superficial skin issues like boils and impetigo to severe, life-threatening conditions like sepsis, pneumonia, and endocarditis. Clinical characteristics vary depending on the site of infection, but common signs include red, painful, or swollen skin, pus-filled blisters, and high fever, with more severe cases involving organ failure, heart or bone infections, or digestive issues like food poisoning. Superficial Skin and Soft Tissue Infections These are the most common manifestations of staph, often appearing as:

Boils and Abscesses: Painful, red lumps or bumps filled with pus just under the skin.

Cellulitis: Red, hot, and swollen skin that can spread.

Impetigo: Shallow, fluid-filled blisters that rupture and leave behind honey-colored crusts.

Folliculitis: A tiny, painful pimple at the base of a hair follicle.

Scalded Skin Syndrome: A severe infection that leads to widespread skin peeling.

Deeper and Systemic Infections: When staph bacteria spread into the bloodstream or deeper tissues, more serious infections can occur.

Sepsis and Septic Shock: Bacteria in the bloodstream cause an overwhelming immune response (sepsis) that can lead to organ failure. Symptoms include fever, chills, fast heart rate, confusion, and cold, clammy skin.

Pneumonia: Infection of the lungs, particularly in people with underlying lung disease or those on mechanical ventilators.

Osteomyelitis: Infection of the bones, often from bacteria spreading through the bloodstream.

Endocarditis: Infection of the heart valves, which can lead to heart failure or stroke.

Bacteremia: The presence of staph bacteria in the bloodstream.

Other Manifestations

Food Poisoning: Occurs when bacteria are ingested with food, causing vomiting and diarrhea.

Mastitis: Breast inflammation and abscesses, often seen in breastfeeding women.

Staphylococcus aureus is a main cause of subclinical mastitis in dairy herds that have successfully controlled major mastitis pathogens. *Staphylococcus aureus* does not normally cause infection on healthy skin; however, if it is allowed to enter the bloodstream or internal tissues, these bacteria may cause a variety of potentially serious infections. This pathogen is implicated in both community-acquired and nosocomial infections with considerable morbidity [44]. The infections are either minor as skin infections, soft tissues and urinary tract infection or more severe and even lethal such as endocarditis, meningitis, bacteremia, pneumonia and toxic shock syndrome [45].

4. Treatment

Systemic anti-MRSA drugs such as Vancomycin remained the mainstay of therapy against MRSA infections in hospitalized patients for decades. Numerous reports do cause MRSA infections in hospitalized patients [46]. The problem of MRSA infections and lack of effective antibiotics other than vancomycin to treat them necessitated the discovery of novel anti-MRSA drugs. The continued efforts of arrival of number of newer anti-MRSA drugs for clinical use in the last 15 years [47]. These drugs include Ceftaroline, Telavancin, Tedizolid and Dalbavancin [48].

5. Conclusion

In Iraq, *Staphylococcus aureus* is associated with common clinical conditions, including skin and soft tissue infections, atopic dermatitis, urinary tract infections (UTIs), and infections from burns, wounds, and burns. A significant challenge is the high prevalence of Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strains, which show robust biofilm formation capabilities. Clinical manifestations range from localized boils and cellulitis to severe systemic diseases like pneumonia and sepsis, particularly in vulnerable patient populations.

Funding sources:

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies.

Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- Becker, K., Ballhausen, B., Köck, R., Kriegeskorte, A. (2014). Methicillin resistance in *Staphylococcus* iso-mecC, a mec homolog associated with zoonotic *S. aureus* lineages. *International Journal of Medical Microbiology*, 304(7), 794-804.
- Kmiciek, W., Szewczyk, E. M. (2017). Gatunki koag- ulazododatnie rodzaju *Staphylococcus*-taksonomia,
- Savini, V., Passeri, C., Mancini, G., Iuliani, O., Marrollo, R., et al. (2013). Coagulase-positive staphylococci: my pet's two faces. *Research in Microbiology*, 5(164), 371-374.
- Rasigade, J. P., Vandenesch, F. (2014). *Staphylococcus aureus*: a pathogen with still unresolved issues. *Infection, genetics and evolution*, 21, 510-514.
- Costa, A. R., Batistão, D. W., Ribas, R. M., Sousa, A. M., Pereira, M. O., et al. (2013). *Staphylococcus aureus* virulence factors and disease.
- Peng, Q.; Tang, X.; Dong, W.; Sun, N.; Yuan, W. A Review of Biofilm Formation of *Staphylococcus aureus* and Its Regulation Mechanism. *Antibiotics* 2022, 12, 12.
- Lowy FD. *Staphylococcus aureus* infections. *N Engl J Med*. 1998 Aug 20;339(8):520-32.
- Harrison, E. M., Weinert, L. A., Holden, M. T., Welch, J. J., Wilson, K., et al. (2014). A shared population of epidemic methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* 15 circulates in humans and companion animals. *MBio*, 5(3), 10-112.
- Guardabassi, L., Larsen, J., Weese, J. S., Butaye, P., Battisti, A., et al. (2013). Public health impact and antimicrobial selection of methicillin-resistant staphylococci in animals. *Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance*, 1(2), 55-62.
- Feltrin, F., Alba, P., Kraushaar, B., Ianzano, A., Argudín, M. A., et al. (2016). A livestock-associated, multidrug-resistant, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* clonal complex 97 lineage spreading in dairy cattle and pigs in Italy. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 82(3), 816-821.
- Cheung, G.Y.C.; Bae, J.S.; Otto, M. Pathogenicity and virulence of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Virulence* 2021, 12, 547-569.
- Linz, M.S.; Mattappallil, A.; Finkel, D.; Parker, D. Clinical Impact of *Staphylococcus Aureus* Skin and Soft Tissue Infections. *Antibiotics* 2023, 12, 557.
- Peng, Q.; Tang, X.; Dong, W.; Sun, N.; Yuan, W. A Review of Biofilm Formation of *Staphylococcus aureus* and Its Regulation Mechanism. *Antibiotics* 2022, 12.
- Siddiqui, A.H.; Koirala, J. Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. In *StatPearls*; StatPearls Publishing: Treasure Island, FL, USA, 2023. Available online: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482221/> (accessed on 9 July 2023).
- Fait, A.; Silva, S.F.; Abrahamsson, J.Å.H.; Ingmer, H. *Staphylococcus aureus* response and adaptation to vancomycin. In *Advances in Microbial Physiology*; Poole, R.K., Kelly, D.J., Eds.; Advances in Microbial Physiology; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2024; Volume 85, pp. 201-258.
- Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska, B.; Kowalewski, C.; Krolak-Ulinska, A.; Marusza, W. Molecular Mechanisms of Drug Resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2022, 23, 8088.
- Rajput, P.; Nahar, K.S.; Rahman, K.M. Evaluation of Antibiotic Resistance Mechanisms in Gram-Positive Bacteria. *Antibiotics* 2024, 13, 1197.
- Jacquemyn, H., Lenaerts, M., Brys, R., Willems, K., Honnay, O., et al. (2013). Among-population variation in *mi- One*, 8(3), e56917.
- Kluytmans, J., van Belkum, A., Verbrugh, H. Nasal carriage of *Staphylococcus aureus*: epidemiology, underlying mechanisms, and associated risks. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 1997; 10:505-520.
- SO, Vaska, van Hal, S.J., Jensen, V.L. Predictors of mortality in *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteremia. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2012; 25:362-386.
- Krumholz, H.M., Normand, S.T., Wang, Y. Twenty-year trends in outcomes for older adults with acute myocardial infarction in the United States. *JAMA NewtOpen.* 2019; 2, e191938.
- Boucher HW, Corey GR. Epidemiology of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2008 Jun 01;46 Suppl 5: S344-9.
- Rasigade JP, Vandenesch F. *Staphylococcus aureus*: a pathogen with still unresolved issues. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2014 Jan; 21:510.
- Chambers HF. Community-associated MRSA—resistance and virulence converge. *N Engl J Med.* 2005 Apr 07;352(14):1485-7.
- Tong SY, Davis JS, Eichenberger E, Holland TL, Fowler VG. *Staphylococcus aureus* infections: epidemiology, pathophysiology, clinical manifestations, and management. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2015 Jul;28(3):603-61.
- DeLeo FR, Diep BA, Otto M. Host defense and pathogenesis in *Staphylococcus aureus* infections. *Infect Dis Clin North Am.* 2009 Mar;23(1):17-34.
- Howden, B.P.; Giulieri, S.G.; Wong Fok Lung, T.; Baines, S.L.; Sharkey, L.K.; Lee, J.Y.H.; Hachani, A.; Monk, I.R.; Stinear, T.P. *Staphylococcus aureus* host interactions and adaptation. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 2023, 21, 380-395.
- 28-Pizon AF, Bonner MR, Wang HE, Kaplan RM. 2006. Ten years of clinical experience with adult meningitis at an urban academic medical center. *J Emerg Med* 30:367-370.
- 29-Aguilar J, Urday-Cornejo V, Donabedian S, Perri M, Tibbetts R, Zervos M. 2010. *Staphylococcus aureus* meningitis: case series and literature review. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 89:117-125.
- 30-Dzupova O, Rozsypal H, Prochazka B, Benes J. 2009. Acute bacterial meningitis in adults: predictors of outcome. *Scand J Infect Dis* 41:348-354.
- 31-Huang WC, Lee CH, Liu JW. 2010. Clinical characteristics and risk factors for mortality in patients with meningitis caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* and vancomycin minimal inhibitory concentrations against these isolates. *J Microbiol Immunol Infect* 43:470-477.
- 32-Durand ML, Calderwood SB, Weber DJ, Miller SI, Southwick FS, Caviness VS Jr, Swartz MN. 1993. Acute bacterial meningitis in adults. A review of 493 episodes. *N Engl J Med* 328:21-28.
- 33-Schlesinger LS, Ross SC, Schaberg DR. 1987. *Staphylococcus aureus* meningitis: a broad-based epidemiologic study. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 66:148-156.
- 34-Teh BW, Slavina MA. 2012. *Staphylococcus aureus* meningitis: barriers to treatment. *Leuk Lymphoma* 53:1443-1444.
- 35-Pintado V, Pazos R, Jimenez-Mejias ME, Rodriguez-Guardado A, Gil A, Garcia-Lechuz JM, Cabellos C, Chaves F, Domingo P, Ramos A, Perez-Cecilia E, Domingo D. 2012. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* meningitis in adults: a multicenter study of 86 cases. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 91:10-17.
- 36-Pintado V, Meseguer MA, Fortun J, Cobo J, Navas E, Quereda C, Corral I, Moreno S. 2002. Clinical study of 44 cases of *Staphylococcus aureus* meningitis. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis* 21:864-868.
- 37-Ray, G. T., Suaya, J. A., Baxter, R. (2013). Microbiology of skin and soft tissue infections in the age of community-acquired methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Diagnostic microbiology and infectious disease*, 76(1), 24-30.
- Rigby, K. M., DeLeo, F. R. (2012, March). Neutrophils in innate host defense against *Staphylococcus aureus* infections. In *Seminars in immunopathology* (Vol. 34, pp. 237-259). Springer-Verlag.
- Greenlee-Wacker, M. C., Rigby, K. M., Kobayashi, S. D., Porter, A. R., DeLeo, F. R., et al. (2014). Phagocytosis of *Staphylococcus aureus* by human neutrophils prevents macrophage efferocytosis and induces programmed necrosis. *The Journal of Immunology*, 192(10), 4709-4717.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

- 40-Spaan, A. N., Henry, T., Van Rooijen, W. J., Perret, M., Badi-ou, C., et al. (2013). The staphylococcal toxin Panton-Val-entine Leukocidin targets human C5a receptors. *Cell host & microbe*, 13(5), 584-594.
- 41-Mariutti, R. B., Tartaglia, N. R., Seyffert, N., de Paula Cas-tro, T. L., Arni, R. K., et al. (2017). Exfoliative toxins of *Staphylococcus aureus*. The Rise of Virulence and Anti-Biotic Resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*.
- 42- Berube, B. J., Bubeck-Wardenburg, J. (2013). *Staphylo-ins*, 5(6), 1140-1166.
- 43-Grumann, D., Nübel, U., Bröker, B. M. (2014). *Staphylo-coccus aureus* toxins—their functions and genetics. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*, 21, 583-592
- 44-Saising, J., Singdam, S., Ongsakul, M., Voravuthi-kunchai, virulence factors in staphylococci isolated from acne le-sions. *Bioscience trends*, 6(4), 160-164.
- 45-Meerlo, M. (2013). Interference of *Staphylococcus au-reus* virulence factors in the blood coagulation system.
- 46-McGuinness, W. A., Malachowa, N., DeLeo, F. R. (2017). Focus: infectious diseases: vancomycin resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*. *The Yale journal of biology and medicine*, 90(2), 269.
- 47- Kurosu, M., Siricilla, S., Mitachi, K. (2013). Advances in MRSA drug discovery: where are we and where do we need to be? *Expert opinion on drug discovery*, 8(9), 1095-1116.45.
- 48- Leuthner, K. D., Buechler, K. A., Kogan, D., Saguros, A treatment of acute bacterial skin and skin structure in-fections (ABSSSI). *Therapeutics and clinical risk man-agement*, 931-940.